

been further substantiated by observation of bands ~ 380 and ~ 450 cm^{-1} in the far-infrared region, attributable⁸ to ν (M-N) and ν (M-O) respectively.

In the electronic spectra, Co(II) complexes give rise to two absorption bands $\sim 18-19$ and ~ 8.6 K.K. regions attributable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(P)$ transition respectively. Position of absorption bands, the extinction coefficient values and magnetic moment suggests an octahedral or distorted octahedral configuration for these complexes. The deep blue cobalt complex shows one intense band at 16.0(980) K.K. due to ${}^4A_g \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition. The other bands are outside the range of spectrophotometer used. Molar absorptivity value and magnetic moment of this complex confirms a tetrahedral geometry.

Three absorption bands appear in case of Nickel(II) complexes in the 8.7-9, 14-15.5 and 25.6 K. K. regions assignable⁹ to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. An octahedral or distorted octahedral structure is suggested for these complexes.

Cu(II) complexes show one broad absorption band ~ 15.0 K.K. region. Though a number of transitions are expected for the copper(II) complex, they are very close in energy and often give rise to one broad band envelope. Hence these complexes are presumably have a planar coordination.

On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral studies, zinc complexes may have a tetrahedral environment around the metal ion.

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Titrimetric Determination of 2, 4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl Chloride with Sodium Methoxide in Non-aqueous Media

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Manuscript received 11 April 1977, revised 31 March 1978,
accepted 4 August 1978

THE unique properties of 2, 4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride¹ has made it extremely valuable to researchers in various fields, and oftentimes one is required to carry out its determination. An iodometric method² for its determination is known. The determination of solutions of 2, 4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride in benzene methanol, nitrobenzene, ethylene chloride, carbon tetrachloride, and dimethyl formamide with sodium methoxide as titrant and thymol blue as indicator, has been studied and is described here. The results are reliable (Table 1) except for dimethylformamide in which case the end point was unreliable.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF 2, 4-DINITROBENZENE-SULPHENYL CHLORIDE (DSC)* WITH SODIUM METHOXIDE

Solvent	DSC, taken mg	DSC, found mg	% Deviation
Benzene-Methanol	10.49	10.47	-0.19
"	21.46	21.50	+0.18
"	22.26	22.23	-0.13
"	32.40	32.47	+0.21
"	51.40	51.52	+0.22
"	52.28	52.18	-0.18
"	71.02	71.02	0.00
"	92.91	100.11	+8.20
"	140.02	139.82	-0.14
"	179.08	179.27	+0.13
Ethylene chloride	10.00	9.98	-0.20
"	25.01	25.01	0.00
"	50.03	50.04	+0.19
"	90.07	90.01	-0.06
Carbon tetrachloride	14.80	14.78	-0.13
"	24.03	24.05	+0.08
"	27.21	27.21	0.00
"	48.80	48.88	+0.06
"	50.82	50.87	+0.09
Nitrobenzene	13.09	13.09	0.00
"	24.60	24.67	+0.28
"	50.01	50.02	+0.02
"	79.03	79.09	+0.07

* Purity of DSC was checked by the iodometric procedure².

Procedure :

The solution of sodium methoxide (0.02 N for samples less than 50 mg and 0.04 N for the remaining samples) is prepared in benzene-methanol³ and standardized against benzoic acid. 2, 4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride⁴ is dissolved in a minimum amount of a-solvent in a conical flask. Twenty-five ml of benzene-methanol (3 : 1) and two drops of thymol blue (0.3% W/V, in methanol) are introduced. The solution is titrated with sodium

methoxide from an automatic burette till the colour changes from yellow to yellowish green. Blank determinations are carried out using the same volumes of the solvents in the respective cases and the values of the blanks are deducted from the values of actual determinations.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. M. M. Bokadia for providing research facilities and to C.S.I.R. for the award of a research fellowship (to N.K.).

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Sensitive Micro Determination of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} with Some Triphenylmethane Dyes in Presence of Micelle Forming Cationic Surfactant

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Manuscript received 5 November 1977, revised 7 August 1978,
accepted 16 August 1978

THE addition of certain long chain quaternary salts render the highly coloured solutions of triphenylmethane dyes to almost colourless. This is expected from the interaction of these dyes with

cation active detergents on account of the relatively high charge within certain pH ranges forming micellar aggregates. The complexes formed with these modified dyes with certain metal ions show extreme rise in the sensitivity and thus yields very sensitive reagents for the micro determination of metal ions.

In our earlier communications, we have reported the use of some triphenylmethane dyes viz., methyl thymol blue (MTB)⁴, chromeazurol S (CAS)⁵, eriochrome azurol B (ECAB)⁶, and solochrome cyanine R (SCR)⁷ in presence of micelle forming cationic surfactants for the micro determination of rare-earths. This paper reports in brief a comparative data of the colour reactions produced between UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} and the above mentioned reagents including pyrocatechol violet (PCV) and Gallein (GAL) in presence of micelle forming cationic surfactant, cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) to explore the possibility of use as sensitive reagents for UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} . Out of these CAS⁵ and SCR⁷ in presence of CTAB have earlier been suggested as sensitive reagents for UO_2^{2+} . CAS⁵ in presence of CTAB has also been reported earlier as a sensitive reagent for Th^{4+} .

Tables 1 and 2 record some useful analytical data for these complexes.

A comparison of these data reveals that ECAB appears to be quite sensitive reagent for UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} . PCV, GAL and SCR can also be recommended as quite sensitive. These reagents are, however, not specific for UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} . However, most of the cations are found not to interfere. The metal ions which interfere in all the cases are Fe^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , In^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Be^{2+} , Ag^+ , Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Sm^{3+} and PO_4^{3-} . Mutual interference of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} was also noted. ECAB is comparatively exposed to lesser interference by foreign ions.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR URANYL COMPLEXES IN PRESENCE OF CTAB

	MTB	ECAB	PCV	GAL
pH of study	6.0	4.5	6.0	3.20
λ_{max} of study (nm)	620	630	660	600
Shift in λ_{max} in presence of CTAB (nm)	600 to 620	620 to 630	600 to 660	540 to 600
Composition of complexes (M:L)	1:1	1:2	1:1	1:1
Formation Constants (log K)	4.2	10.1	5.0	5.7
Effective photometric range (ppm)	1.19-3.37	0.27-0.81	0.59-1.78	2.1-4.18
Molar absorptivity	3.8×10^4	9.6×10^4	6.24×10^4	4.16×10^4
Sensitivity (Sandell) $\mu g/cm^2$	0.0049	0.0015	0.0031	0.0040

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR Th^{4+} COMPLEXES IN PRESENCE OF CTAB

	MTB	SCR	ECAB	PCV	GAL
pH of study	5.0	4.5	4.5	5.8	3.20
λ_{max} of study (nm)	600	600	600	660	590
Shift in λ_{max} in presence of CTAB (nm)	Nil	520 to 600	570 to 600	600 to 660	540 to 590
Composition of Complexes (M:L)	1:1	1:2	1:2	1:1	1:1
Formation Constants (log K)	4.2	10.1	10.1	5.0	5.6
Effective photometric range (ppm)	1.15-3.38	1.11-3.48	0.55-1.48	0.53-1.74	1.19-3.62
Molar absorptivity	3.43×10^4	7.20×10^4	8.56×10^4	5.19×10^4	4.71×10^4
Sensitivity (Sandell) $\mu g/cm^2$	0.0049	0.0019	0.0015	0.0034	0.0037